

Employee Engagement and High Performance Work System: An Empirical Study

Vol. I, No. I (2016) | Page: 114 – 131
p- ISSN: 2616-955X
e-ISSN: 2663-7030
L-ISSN: 2616-955X
DOI: 10.31703/grr.2016(I-I).09

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Abstract

Organizations and researchers have focused their attention on means and ways to gain more advantage on less resource consumption in the competitive working environment. Hence, channeling human resource practices to gain maximum return on investment is focused upon. Our data are collected from the banking sector of Pakistan from a sample of 400 employees. The theme is to analyze the association of the variables at multi-level, that is to say. The data is collected from two pools of respondents. The first includes the staff level employees and the second the middle management employees using an adapted questionnaire comprising two sections for each pool respectively. A reliability test, correlation analysis and regression analysis are conducted on the data. The findings of the result support a positive association of independent variable with dependent variables (department and employee level measures of High Performance Work Systems (HPWS)).

Key Words: Employee engagement, HPWS, Commitment, Competitive Market, Performance

Introduction

The contemporary dynamic business environment is striving for in depth analysis on high performing work systems. Extensive thought should be paid to any association that works through the inspirational impacts defined as 'high-commitment' or 'high-involvement' representative results. This examination features different elite work practices and commitment in with worker relationships, frame of mind and conduct level. The examination recognizes the linkage between representative commitment and superior work practices, which bring about upgrading worker conduct and frame of mind emphatically and decisively influencing worker profitability and authoritative execution.

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Worker commitment is presently a noteworthy worry all over the globe in the circles of the board. This idea is picking up critical attention among the administrators and scholarly professionals in Pakistan too. Regardless of the significance of representative commitment, there is still little research carried out so far so as to distinguish the precursors of worker commitment. This examination endeavors to characterize distinctive ideas of 'drew in worker' by various specialists in various periods. A hopeful individual profoundly centered around work, devoted, retained, excited and willing to go an additional mile, puts additional exertion so as to add to the hierarchical accomplishment on a long-haul premise. So, the exploration proposes a critical connection between human asset practices and worker dimensions of commitment in the association.

In this context, the relationship is explained on the basis of social exchange theory. In this current research importance of employee engagement and its declining levels have also been discussed across the globe. At the end, the present study also highlights the thin literature, in Pakistan's context and beyond, in the domain of HR management. Key objectives and the contribution of current research are to explore the impact of employee engagement and high-performance practices in combination, on two performance levels, in banks. These are employee level and department level. The study is based on lower level employees and middle level managers of the banking sector.

Literature Review

Globally changing business dynamics are compelling firms to adopt modern and new business strategies to survive in a competitive world. Organizations are motivated to adopt HR practices in support of the new organization strategies by knowing the new trends in the market for competitive advantage. In Anglophone countries, scholars related to management have been introducing the concepts of employee management, which affects the structure of the organization form top to bottom.

However, it is significant for management and practitioners to conduct reliable human resource management internally, affected by the reality of deliberate tensions frequently found in firms due to dissimilar stakeholders' competing goals in an organisation which is engaged in recreating a major role in its administration (Boxall & Purcell 2003).

Principles of HPWS

There are four principles which are the building blocks for successful HPWS implementation. These principles, which provide support for HPWS, are performance-reward and alignment, egalitarianism, employee engagement, knowledge development, and shared information, (Bolander & Snell 2010).

According to Bohlander & Snell (ibid. 2010), egalitarianism is an important principle. According to this, as the power separation between leading edge staff and best administration is decreased, the workplace becomes communitarian and group based and more in natural. Popularity tends to fulfill the needs of representatives so that they feel a greater sense of belonging and connection to an organization. According to this principle, employees work as a team and more cooperatively toward the common goal for the betterment of their organization. Performance and productivity can be improved if there is collaboration among employees, in a more cooperative way at multi-levels (Bohlander & Snell 2010). But this principle does not work for the taller organizations, with a large hierarchy of jobs. Human resource practices which solicit input from employees through suggestion systems, surveys, and focus groups, provide assistance with power moving down in organizations (Bohlander & Snell 2010).

Employee Engagement and HPWS

Employee attitude is alternatively taken as employee engagement (Appelbaum et al. 2000, Boxall & Purcell 2011). Therefore, engagement is originally defined as “a positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind that is characterized by vigor, dedication and absorption” (Schaufeli, Salanova, Gonzalez-Romá, & Bakker 2002, p.74). Schaufeli et al. (ibid.) and Bakker and van Rhenen (2009 p.895) concluded that absorption is a concept which is more related to the flow concept and plays a less significant and different role within the engagement concept.

Rich, Lepine and Crawford (2010) and Kahn (1990) in addition, argued that, that because of the fact that employees’ work roles are defined by the behavioral expectations of the firm, physical energy investments result most likely in meeting expectations. Therefore, the study is focused on the vigor or physical engagement that can be characterized as “high levels of energy and mental resilience while working, the willingness to invest effort in one’s work, and persistence even in the face of difficulties” (Schaufeli et al. 2002, p.74). Thus, employees who are engaged, have high energy levels.

Appelbaum et al. (2000) found evidence that human resource practices, based upon ability, opportunity to perform and motivation lead to discretionary effort. Macy and Schneider (2008) defined the concept of physical engagement as the discretionary effort that is described as walking the extra mile for the firm or organization. So, employees go beyond what is expected or required typically when employees perceive HPWS is which based upon the AMO model (Appelbaum et al. (2000).

Appelbaum et al. (2000) furnished proof that can be clarified with the assistance of the social trade hypothesis of Blau (1964). The social trade hypothesis or SET is characterized by Blau (1964 p. 91) as "intentional activities of people that are persuaded by the profits they are relied upon to bring and ordinarily do in

reality bring from others". The SET or social trade hypothesis is comprehended as not the same as a relationship of financial trade as it focuses on the social structure "as an arrangement of social relations among performing artists (both individual and corporate), where the relations include the trading of esteemed things" (Cook & Whitmeyer 1992, p. 110). In this manner, when the HR practices are executed by an association which goes for representative advancement to accomplish their objectives at work, by taking an additional mile for the association representatives may be progressively occupied with their activity.

In terms of the present study, the structure applied has been proposed in figure 1, which elucidates the connection between worker commitment and elite work frameworks. It demonstrates the segments of worker commitment and the HPWS measures. In figure 1 we can see the relationship of three components of worker commitment and the proportions of elite work frameworks at representative dimension and at the office level. All the inferred factors, which are distinguished in the figure will be examined in the discussion of demographic factors. For example, sexual orientation, age, capability, experience and assignment are taken as control factors. There are six connections in the figure, which are theorized as H1a, H1b, H2a, H2b, H3a and H3b. In figure 1, the first relationship appears between the components of representative commitment, devotion, life and ingestion and worker level proportions of HPWSs including professions of the board, preparing, cooperation, data sharing, correspondence, and reward framework. Other relationships are related to the connection between dedication vigor and absorption and department level measures of HPWSs including recruitment and selection, promotion, information sharing, appraisal system, attitude survey, communication and the flexible working.

IV
Employee engagement

DV
HPWS

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypotheses:

H1a: There is a positive association between vigor and employee level measures of High Performance Work System.

H1b: There is a positive connection between vigor and department level measures of High Performance Work System.

H2a: There is a positive link between dedication and employee level measures of High Performance Work System.

H2b: There is a positive association between dedication and department level measures of High Performance Work System.

H3a: There is a positive connection between absorption and employee level measures of High Performance Work System.

H3b: There is a positive association between absorption and department level measures of High Performance Work System.

Methodology

Surveys are utilized as a research instrument for the gathering of information and gaining the impressions of the center dimension supervisors and lower level representatives in the banking area of Pakistan.

The questionnaire of the research is adapted by combining two separate and different instruments. A demographics section gathers information about age, gender, and experience in job, qualification, and designation of the respondents. The purpose of the study, importance of completing the questionnaire and general instructions were personally explained to the respondents in the covering letter, which was attached with each questionnaire.

The study is a multi-level study, where two different questionnaires were developed for both levels, employees at staff level and middle managerial levels. The section or questions regarding employee engagement were the same for both the levels and the questions for the measures of HPWS were different for both levels. The items in the questionnaire were carefully placed in different sections to avoid any uncertainty and confusion. The first section covered the questions related to employee engagement dimensions and the second section covered HPWS and its measures.

The employees from the lower staff level and employees from the middle managerial level in KSE listed commercial banks situated in Rawalpindi and Islamabad form the population of the study. The number of total, international, national, both private and public sector, commercial banks in Pakistan is 36 and the banks listed in KSE and located in the twin cities are 25 in number. Commercial banks have 9,087 branches all over Pakistan. All of the listed commercial banks have 8,296 branches all over Pakistan and among them 452 branches in Rawalpindi Islamabad. Mostly branches are in urban areas and only those banks have branches in rural areas that have a nationalization history. In each branch the number of managers, depends upon the volume of the branch deposits.

The banks are divided in three regions (northern region, central region and southern region) in Pakistan's territory. It is a very difficult and challenging task to collect data on all middle level managers working in the whole region and in the main cities such as Rawalpindi and Islamabad. There are 25 banks located in the twin cities and listed in KSE in all three key regions and their presence can be noticed in only urban areas. So randomly, 400 questionnaires were sent to the banks' branches in Rawalpindi Islamabad through post, fax, and email, and some branches were visited in person.

Data Analysis

The centre of this investigation is the banking area and banks recorded in KSE and situated in Pakistan are focused on for information gathering. Information is gathered by means of polls from the directors and lower level administration of the individual associations. As the number of participants in the proposed examination was unclear so non-likelihood helpful inspecting was utilized for the gathering of the information. The example measure for this examination was around 350-500 representatives from different business banks in Islamabad and Rawalpindi. Information was accumulated through a self-regulated overview survey. The surveys were conveyed through different ways; physically, through postal administrations and electronically. A pilot test was conducted on the example of 40 respondents to check the consistent quality and legitimacy of the adjusted poll. To analyze the gathered information, the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was utilized for the relapse and relationship examination.

To study the association, first a pilot study was conducted. For this purpose, 40 questionnaires regarding employee level measures of HPWS were sent to lower management including supervisors and employees and 40 questionnaires of department level measures of HPWS were delivered to middle management including branch managers, operation managers and others. After collecting the data from department level and employee level, correlations at both levels were made individually. Then further data was collected and a regression analysis was applied.

Table 1. Reliability Analysis of the Instrument at Department Level

Variables	N of items	Cronbach's Alpha
DED	6	.866
Vigor	5	.913
ABS	6	.841
HPWS	26	.953

Table 1. shows the reliability statistics for the instruments used in this study and indicates that the scales for DED, VIG, ABS, HPWS were highly reliable being global in nature, with alpha values ranging from 0.841 to 0.953

Pearson Correlations Matrix (at Department level)

The Pearson correlation test was conducted to measure the strength of the relationship among variables of the study. It forecasts the changes in one variable value as the result in the change of another variable. Its scale ranges from -1.0 to +1.0, and the relationship strength at these values gives the best predictions. Thus, a Pearson correlation was used to measure the correlation between the hypothesized variables HPWS, dedication, vigor and absorption.

Table 2. Correlation Analysis

	DED	VIG	ABS	HPWS
DED	1			
VIG	.491**	1		
ABS	.657**	.686**	1	
HPWS	.693**	0.306	.399*	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The correlation among the variables under study at department level is depicted in the table above. Correlation is denoted by (r). This is determined for the predictors which are dedication, vigor and absorption the dimensions of employee engagement and the outcome variable that is HPWS, at both levels (department level and employee level) individually. So, in this matrix Correlation coefficients (r) for the predictors DED, VIG, and ABS are r=0.693, r= 0.309 and r= 0.399 respectively with $p \leq 0.001$ which shows a positive and significant relationship with the dependent variable HPWS. In other relationship (r) values of independent variable dedication (DED) for the other independent variables vigor (VIG) and absorptions (ABS) the results are r=0.491 and r=0.657 respectively showing positive and significant relationship. Likewise the (r) value of IV VIG for other IV that is ABS is r = 0.686. The above table depicts positive relationships among all variables under study.

Regression Analysis (at Department level)

Regression analysis is used to check the impact of independent variables as in this study dedication, vigor and absorption on the measures of HPWS, a dependent variable. So, regression is applied to test the hypothesis through SPSS. As above,

regression analysis was carried out for department level and employee level individually to test the hypothesis.

Regression (Dedication and HPWS)

The table 3 shows the simple regression analysis between the dedication and HPWS at department level.

Table 3. The Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.587 ^a	.345	.338	.79371
a. Predictors: (Constant), DED				

Table 4. The Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.661	.483		3.442	.001
	DED	.625	.091	.587	6.845	.000
a. Dependent Variable: HPWS						

These tables give the R and R² values. The R estimation addresses the direct relationship and is 0.587, which demonstrates an abnormal state of association. The R² value demonstrates the measure of the supreme assortment in the poor variable: that's to say HPWS can be clarified by the free factor, DED. So, R Square is 34.5%. The statistics show that the DED accounts for 34.5% of variance in HPWS, which is not very large. Thus, the regression model fits the data well.

The ANOVA table shows how well the regression equation fits the data (that is, predicts the DV). It shows that the regression model forecasts the HPWS significantly well. The Sig. column shows statistical significance for the tested regression model. Here $p < 0.0005$, that is less than .05, which shows that the regression model predicts the DV that is HPWS with statistical significance.

The coefficient table gives information to predict (DV HPWS from (IV) DED and also says whether IV contributes significantly to the model (by showing the sig. value). The Beta values show wheter there is an increment of 01 unit in dedication, and association with HPWS will be increased by 58.7 percent. So, based on this information the hypothesis is accepted.

Regression Analysis (Vigor and HPWS)

A simple regression analysis between the vigor and HPWS at department level is depicted in the table below;

Table 5. The Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.327 ^a	.107	.097	.92681
a. Predictors: (Constant), VIG				

The R value represents simple correlation; the value is calculated to be of 0.327 which indicates a moderate degree of correlation.

Table 6. The Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.250	.520		6.251	.000
	VIG	.327	.100	.327	3.261	.002
a. Dependent Variable: HPWS						

The R2 estimation demonstrates the measure of the full assortment in the dependent variable: that's to say HPWS, can be cleared up by the free factor being clarified by the independent variable, VIG. So, R Square is 10.7%. It is deducted that the VIG accounts for 10.7% of variance in HPWS, which is very low.

For the second self-ruling variable,, Beta tells us that if there is an expansion of one unit in energy, association with HPWS will be increased by 32.7 percent. So, based on this information an association between vigor and HPWS is accepted.

Regression Analysis (Absorption & HPWS)

Table 7 shows a simple regression analysis between the absorption and HPWS at department level.

Table 7. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.460 ^a	.211	.202	.87086
a. Predictors: (Constant), ABS				

The R value represents the simple correlation. The value is calculated to be 0.460, which indicates a high degree of correlation.

Table 8. The Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.458	.511		4.808	.000
	ABS	.467	.096	.460	4.883	.000

a. Dependent Variable: HPWS

The R² estimation demonstrates the measure of the full-scale assortment in the dependent variable: that's to say HPWS, can be elucidated by the free factor, ABS. So, R-Square is 21.1%. It shows that the ABS accounts for 21.1% of variance in HPWS, which is very low.

For third free factor that is absorption, Beta regard tells us that if there is an enlargement of one unit in absorption, association with HPWS will be increased by 46 per cent. So based on this information the hypothesis is accepted

Multiple Regression (at Department level)

Table 9 is showing the multiple regression analysis by taking all the independent variables, which are dedication, vigor and absorption and HPWS. This analysis will let us know about the variation in HPWS by the dimensions of employee engagement as a whole, at departmental parameter.

Table 9. The Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.588 ^a	.345	.323	.80254

a. Predictors: (Constant), ABS, VIG, DED

In multiple regressions like simple regression first model of consideration is Model summary table. Table 9 also provides the values of R, R-square and Adj. R square, which are used to determine, how well the regression model fits the data. Here R value shows the multiple correlation coefficient, and is considered one value of the quality of prediction of DV (HPWS). So here 0.588 indicates a good level of prediction

Table 10. The Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.639	.534		3.067	.003
	DED	.602	.143	.565	4.218	.000
	VIG	-.008	.122	-.008	-.068	.946
	ABS	.035	.160	.035	.220	.827

a. Dependent Variable: HPWS

Here R square (coefficient of assurance) demonstrates the extent of difference in DV that is clarified by IV. Here R square is 0.345, so that our IVs clarify 34.5% of fluctuation of DV. A balanced R square is utilized to report precisely the information.

F estimation is identified with the testing of invalid theory: that there is no direct connection between the factors, or it can be said R square is equivalent to zero. Here F is $(3.87) = 15.292$ which is huge and there is a direct connection between factors in the model. Likewise in multiple regressions, where the independent variables that are dedication, vigor and absorption, the beta value tells us how much DV varies with an IV when other IVs are constant. So, if there is a change of one unit in one IV (DED), the association with HPWS will be changed by 60.2%. positively. This rate of change in other absorption with the change in association with HPWS is -8% but here there is a negative relationship such that if there is a change in one unit in vigor, association with HPWS decreased by 8%. So, the hypothesis is rejected regarding association between vigor and HPWS at department level.

Regression Analysis at Employee level

Table no 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 are showing the simple regression analysis between DED, VIG, absorption and HPWS individually.

Regression Analysis (DED & HPWS) at Employee level

The table 11 shows the simple regression analysis between the dedication and HPWS at employee level.

Table 11. The Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.821 ^a	.675	.674	.59587

a. Predictors: (Constant), DED

The estimation of *R* depicts the association as 0.821 , which is high.

Table 12. The Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	.928	.164		5.642	.000
	DED	.781	.032	.821	24.319	.000

a. Dependent Variable: HPWS

The R2 exhibits the measure of the hard and fast assortment in the DV, i.e., HPWS can be illuminated by the IV; devotion. The incentive for R Square is 67.5%. The outcome demonstrates that DED represents 67.5% of fluctuation in HPWS, which is high. For first autonomous variable that is commitment, Beta esteem tells if there is an addition of one unit in dedication, association with HPWS will be increased by 78.1 percent. So based on this information association between dedication and HPWS is accepted.

Regression Analysis (VIG & HPWS) at Employee level

The table 13 shows the simple regression analysis between the vigor and HPWS at employee level.

Table 13. The Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.692 ^a	.479	.477	.75430

a. Predictors: (Constant), VIGOR

The estimation of *R* value shows the association as 0.692 , which is high.

Table 14. The Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.523	.209		7.270	.000
	VIGOR	.646	.040	.692	16.184	.000

a. Dependent Variable: HPWS

The R2 information shows the measure of the total assortment in the dependent variable, i.e., HPWS can be elucidated by the free factor, VIG. So, R Square is

47.9%. The result shows that the VIG accounts for 47.9% of variance in HPWS, which is high.

For the second free factor, force, the Beta estimation tells us that if there is an addition of one unit in power, relationship with HPWS will be expanded by 69.2 percent. So dependent on this data, a relationship among power and HPWS is acknowledged.

Regression Analysis (Abs & HPWS) at Employee level

The table 15 shows the simple regression analysis between the absorption and HPWS at employee level.

Table 15. The Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.741 ^a	.550	.548	.70132
a. Predictors: (Constant), ABS				

The R estimation tells about the basic association which is 0.741 , which depicts high in value..

Table 16. The Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.189	.200		5.948	.000
	ABS	.716	.038	.741	18.646	.000
a. Dependent Variable: HPWS						

The R2 data depict the value of complete change in the other variable; thus R Square is 55%. The result shows that the ABS accounts for 55% of variance in HPWS, which is very high. For the third independent variable, absorption, the Beta value tells us that if there is an increment of one unit in absorption, association with HPWS will be increased by 32.7 percent. So, based on this information an association between absorption and HPWS is accepted.

Multiple Regression Analysis (at employee level)

The multiple regression analysis is depicted in the table below by taking all the independent variables, which are dedication, vigor and absorption and HPWS.

This analysis will let us know about the variation in HPWS by the dimensions of employee engagement as a whole, at employee level.

Table 17. The Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.844 ^a	.712	.709	.56314
a. Predictors: (Constant), ABS, VIGOR, DED				

Here R value shows the multiple correlation coefficient, and is considered one value of the quality of prediction of DV (HPWS). So here 0.844 indicates a very good level of prediction

Table 18 The Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.487	.173		2.821	.005
	DED	.574	.055	.603	10.407	.000
	VIGOR	.216	.044	.231	4.923	.000
	ABS	.073	.060	.076	1.221	.223
a. Dependent Variable: HPWS						

As in multiple regression for the independent variables dedication, vigor and absorption, the Beta value tells us how much DV varies with a IV when other IVs are constant. So if there is a change of one unit in one IV (DED), association with HPWS will be changed by 57.4 %. positively. As with this rate of change in other IVs, the changes in association with HPWS are 21.6% and 7.3%.

Multiple regressions tests are conducted to predict the impact of HPWS from dedication, vigor and absorption. These variables significantly and statistically predict HPWS where $F(3,283)$, $p < 0.005$, $R = 0.712$, mean all three variables added significantly to the prediction $P < 0.5$

Conclusion

Based on the analysis, the findings of the examination conclusively reached the outcome that the survival of Pakistan's financial industry relies on its HRM practices as reflected through the view of the senior and center dimension administrators. The motivation behind the examination was to discover the likelihood of positive results helping to gain the upper hand through representative commitment and HPWS in the relentless challenge of the Pakistani financial sector. The target of the investigation was to demonstrate that adjustment of elite

work practices can prompt more elevated amounts of inspiration, which can make workers increasingly devoted, lively and fulfilled. Additionally, it is seen that the representatives in the banks have a positive methodology for worker commitment. The discoveries demonstrate the job of HPWS and representative commitment and their relationship in Pakistan's banks.

Recommendations

There are the following constraints in this investigation. The limits of this investigation would suggest a concentration on future research. It is a cross sectional examination where all information was gathered at a specific time, so the factors and investigation are confined to that specific time. For future research it is prescribed to direct longitudinal investigation that is to gather information from a similar example of individuals time and again over some stretch of time, with the goal that the scientist may break down the measurements in more significant detail. This investigation is restricted to just the administration area of Pakistan, that is the financial sector. Information is gathered just from the business banking sector of the twin urban communities including Rawalpindi and Islamabad. For future analysis it is recommended to prepare a similar report on different sectors in Pakistan including mechanical and instructive.

References

- Adams, J.S. (1963). Toward an Understanding of in- equity. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 67, 422-36.
- Appelbaum, E., Bailey, T., Berg, P., & Kalleberg, A. (2000). *Manufacturing Advantage: Why High Performance Work Systems Pay Off*. Ithaca, NY: ILR Press.
- Asad, A., Hussain, R. I., Nayyab, H., Ashraf, M. & Adnan, S. (2011). Impact of hr practices on employee engagement in banking sector of Pakistan. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 3(1), 409-416.
- Arthur, J. B. (1994). Effects of human resource systems on manufacturing performance and turnover. *Academy of Management journal*, 37(3), 670–687.
- Arthur, W. B., & Queen's University (1992). On learning and adaptation in the economy. Institute for Economic Research, Queen's University.
- Becker B. E. & Huselid M. A. (1998). High performance work systems and firm performance: A synthesis of research and managerial implications. *Research in Personnel and Human Resources Journal*, 16(1): 53-101.
- Bakker, A. B., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2008). Positive organizational behavior: Engaged employees in flourishing organizations. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 29(2), 147-154
- Barney, J. B. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of management*, 17(1), 99–120.
- Barney, J. B. (2001). Resource-based theories of competitive advantage: A ten-year retrospective on the resource-based view. *Journal of management*, 27(6), 643.
- Batt, R. (2000). Strategic Segmentation and Frontline Services: Matching Customers, Employees, and Human Resource Systems. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*. 11(3):540-61.

- Bateman, T.S., & Crant, J.M. (1993). The Proactive Component of Organizational Behavior: A Measure and Correlates. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 14, 103–118.
- Beer, M., Voelpel, S., Aspinwall, L. G., & Taylor, S. E. (1997). A stitch in time: selfregulation and proactive coping. *Psychological Bulletin*, 121, 417-436.
- Blau, P. M. (1964). *Exchange and power in social life*. Transaction Publishers.
- Becker, B., & Gerhart, B. (1996). The impact of human resource management on organizational performance: Progress and prospects. *Academy of Management Journal*, 39(4), 779–801.
- Boxall, P., & Purcell, J. (2000). Strategic human resource management: where have we come from and where should we be going?. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 2(2), 183–203.
- Boxall, P. F., & Purcell, J. (2003). *Strategy and human resource management* (Vol. 219). Palgrave Macmillan Basingstoke, UK.
- Brown, S.P & Leigh, T.W (1996) A New Look at Psychological Climate and Its Relationship to Job Involvement, Effort, and Performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 81(4), 358-368
- Baard, P. P., Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2004). Intrinsic Need Satisfaction: A Motivational Basis of Performance and Well-Being in Two Work Settings. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 34(10), 2045-2068.
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2008). Towards a model of work engagement. *Career development international*, 13(3), 209-223.
- Brown, S. P., & Leigh, T. W. (1996). A new look at psychological climate and its relationship to job involvement, effort, and performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 81, 358–368
- H. J., Shin, K. H., & Swanger, N. (2009). Burnout and engagement: A comparative analysis using the Big Five personality dimensions. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 28(1), 96-104.